

Redefining Next Generation Fronthaul for the Interplay Between Communication and Sensing Data

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EXTENDED ABSTRACT

The evolution towards 6G networks is expected to introduce a new paradigm shift, with the integration and interplay of both communication and sensing (C&S) capabilities [1]. This transformation is not merely intended to enhancing communication capabilities via sensing but it also allows new business opportunities for mobile network operators (MNOs) by exploiting and, possibly, monetizing the processed sensing data itself. This talk examines the repercussions on the fronthaul (FH) infrastructure design, impacted by the expected increased communication data rates in 6G and the influx of diverse sensing data volumes. We further discuss the general challenges and opportunities presented by integrating sensing data, highlighting its critical role in enriching 6G networks, for example by enabling applications such as target detection, tracking, and displacement monitoring.

The focus is set on Centralized Radio Access Network (C-RAN) deployments, whereby the digital signal processing is 'split' between the geo-distributed Active Antenna Units (AAUs) and the centralized baseband unit (BBU). In this setup, the fronthaul becomes the interfacing link transporting data between the BBU and a several AAUs. Such deployments offer increased maintainability, flexibility, upgradability, as well as improved inter-cell coordination features [2]. We propose and explore the novel concept of sensing functional 'split' (S-split hereon) architectures, drawing parallels from well-known functional split in the communication's domain (C-split) [3], and discuss their impact on the provision of diverse network features in C&S domains. Further, we outline and evaluate design strategies for an optimal design of both C-splits and S-split, considering monostatic versus bi-static sensing paradigms and the dimensioning requirements for fronthaul to support various splits. We give insights on the foreseeable data volumes and latency requirements sensing will bring and the implications on fronthaul capacity, providing quantitative analyses derived from use cases such as, e.g., target detection and displacement monitoring.

In addressing the challenges and fronthaul design considerations, we propose a 3-phased approach for fronthaul evolution: starting with 'coexistence', followed by 'harmonization', and culminating in 'integration'. Each phase introduces a tighter level of integration between the C&S subsystems. This entails the examination of different fixed fronthaul capacity sharing options, with the adoption of traffic prioritization, and compression optimization [4] to uphold latency constraints while still guaranteeing C&S quality of service (QoS). The talk concludes with an insight into the future, where traffic prediction methodologies can be used to enhance fronthaul utilization, steering towards an adaptive and scalable network infrastructure which can respond to the intricate C&S interplay within future 6G networks.

Keywords: Centralized Radio Access Networks (C-RAN), wireless, fronthaul, integrated sensing and communications (ISAC), 6G.

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